

Hygroscopic Phase Field Failure Modelling of Composite Materials

ICCM23, Belfast, 30th July-4th August 2023

Dr. Wei Tan

Senior Lecturer in Mechanical Engineering
Queen Mary University of London

With excellent contributions from:

Kit Au-Yeung (QMUL), Emilio Martínez-Pañeda (Imperial), Adria Quintanas Corominas (Imperial, BSC), and many others.

[Bond and Smith, 2006]

Outline

1. Motivation

2. Methods

3. Results

Background: Offshore energy

- Offshore energy is an effective solution to produce clean energy and mitigate global warming, including wind, wave, tidal and thermal, etc.
- Global offshore wind is expected to reach **2000 GW** by 2050. Wave and tidal energy would represent an additional **350 GW**.
- This can power ~ **2 billion** household, ~ **50%** of the population.
- This highlights the need for further investment and research in this area.

[1] Bastien Taormina, PhD thesis, 2019

[2] <https://www.irena.org/publications/2021/Jul/Offshore-Renewables-An-Action-Agenda-for-Deployment>

Problem: Material degradations

- Lightweight **composite materials** have been widely used in offshore energy (e.g. wind blades).
- In service, the offshore structures continuously experiences **extreme weather conditions**.
- Particularly the effect of **loading conditions, temperature, moisture** is detrimental.

Moisture: Multiphysics degradation mechanisms

- Exposure to moisture can degrade the mechanical properties of composite materials.

▣ Plastication or Hydrolysis

- ▣ Moisture diffusion
- ▣ Matrix swelling

- ▣ Interface debonding

- **State-of-art: Modelling moisture-assisted degradation of composites remains relatively unexplored.**
- **Our aim: To develop fully-coupled computational models for moisture-assisted degradation.**

[1] David A., Bond and Paul A. Smith. (2006): 249-268.

State-of-art: Modelling moisture-assisted degradation in composites remains relatively unexplored

- The **moisture transport** problem was not explicitly resolved and, instead, a uniform moisture distribution was assumed.

- “**Crack filter theory**” is proposed to regularise the sharp fibre-matrix interface and controls the moisture fluxes.
- Finding the coefficients for the crack filter functions remains a challenge.

[1] Arash, B., Exner, W., Rolfes, R. Engineering with Computers (2022).

[2] Ye, J.-Y., Zhang, L.-W Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering 388, 114213 (2022).

Outline

1. Motivation

2. Methods

3. Results

Fully coupled multiphysics phase field model

□ The interplay between **moisture diffusion**, **hygroscopic expansion**, **crack evolution** and **stress redistribution**.

Mass transport: Moisture diffusion

- **Fick's law** C - moisture concentration

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} = D \nabla^2 C$$

D - Diffusion coefficient

t - time

- **Chemical potential of moisture**

$$\mu = \mu^0 + RT \ln C - \bar{V}_H \sigma_H$$

- **Mass flux (Linear Onsager)**

$$\mathbf{J} = -\frac{DC}{RT} \nabla \mu = -D \nabla C + \frac{D}{RT} C \bar{V}_H \nabla \sigma_H$$

- **Balance equation (mass conservation)**

$$\frac{dC}{dt} + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{J} = 0$$

- **The weak form of moisture diffusion:**

$$\int_{\Omega} \left[\delta C \left(\frac{1}{D} \frac{dC}{dt} \right) + \nabla C \nabla \delta C - \nabla \delta C \left(\frac{\bar{V}_H C}{RT} \nabla \sigma_H \right) \right] dV = -\frac{1}{D} \int_{\partial \Omega_q} \delta C q dS$$

Deformation: The effect of moisture

Moisture concentration leads to the presence of hygroscopic strains:

➤ **Hygroscopic strain**

$$\varepsilon^m = \alpha (C - C_0)$$

➤ **Cauchy stress**

$$\sigma_0 = \mathcal{C}\varepsilon^e = \mathcal{C} (\varepsilon - \varepsilon^m)$$

➤ **Moisture-dependent fracture toughness:**

$$G_c^I = \begin{cases} a_1 \exp(a_2 C) + a_1 \exp(a_2 C) & C < C_0 \\ G_{c0} & C \geq C_0 \end{cases}$$

Damage: Phase field fracture model

- **Griffith's energy balance [Griffith, 1920]** Π - total potential energy

$$\frac{d\Pi}{dA} = \frac{d\psi}{dA} + G_c = 0$$

A - crack area

Ψ - strain energy density

G_c - critical energy release rate

- **Variational approach to fracture [Francfort and Marigo, 1998]**

$$\min \Pi = \int_{\Omega} \psi(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) dV + \int_{\Gamma} G_c dS - \int_{\Omega} b \cdot \delta u dV - \int_{\partial\Omega_h} h \cdot \delta u dS$$

- **Phase field fracture [Bourdin et al., 2008, Miehe et al., 2010]**

$$\min \Pi_{\ell} = \int_{\Omega} (1 - \phi)^2 \psi(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) dV + \int_{\Omega} G_c \left(\frac{\phi^2}{2\ell} + \frac{\ell}{2} |\nabla\phi|^2 \right) dV - \int_{\Omega} b \cdot \delta u dV - \int_{\partial\Omega_h} h \cdot \delta u dS$$

- **Coupled field equations:**

$$(1 - \phi)^2 \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{0} \quad \text{in } \Omega$$

$$G_c \left(\frac{\phi}{\ell} - \ell \Delta\phi \right) - 2(1 - \phi) \psi = 0 \quad \text{in } \Omega$$

ϕ - damage variable

ℓ - length scale

- **Crack increases the diffusion coefficient:**

$$D = D_0 [1 + k_d H(\phi) (\phi - \phi_{th})]$$

Phase field: matrix and fibre cracking

Diffuse interface (Phase field)

Challenge: **Sharp interfaces** can not model the moisture diffusion and represent the graded interface.

- A diffuse transition zone between the fibre and matrix:

$$\begin{cases} \vartheta - \ell_\vartheta^2 \nabla^2 \vartheta = 0 & \text{in } \Omega \\ \vartheta(0) = 1 & \text{on } \Gamma \\ \nabla \vartheta \cdot \mathbf{n} = 0 & \text{on } \partial\Omega \end{cases}$$

- An interpolation function:

$$G_c = h(\vartheta) \left(G_c^{(i)} - G_c^I \right) + G_c^I$$

$$D = h(\vartheta) \left(D^{(i)} - D_I \right) + D_I$$

(a) phase field interface indicator

(b) interpolation of material toughness across the interface

Finite element discretisation

The weak form for the **coupled deformation-phase field fracture problem** is formulated as:

$$\int_{\Omega} \left[(1 - \phi)^2 \boldsymbol{\sigma}_0 : \delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} - 2(1 - \phi) \delta \phi \mathcal{H} + G_c \left(\frac{\phi}{\ell} \delta \phi + \ell \nabla \phi \cdot \nabla \delta \phi \right) \right] dV = 0$$

The **deformation, diffusion** and **phase field** fracture problems are weakly coupled.

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{K}^u & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \mathbf{K}^\phi & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \mathbf{K}^C \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{u} \\ \phi \\ C \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & M \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\mathbf{u}} \\ \dot{\phi} \\ \dot{C} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{r}^u \\ \mathbf{r}^\phi \\ \mathbf{r}^C \end{bmatrix}$$

It is solved in an incremental manner, using the Newton-Raphson method. The solution scheme follows a so-called **staggered** approach.

Outline

1. Motivation


```
graph TD; A[1. Motivation] --> B[2. Methodologies]; B --> C[3. Results];
```

2. Methodologies

3. Results

The effect of moisture on fracture toughness: Mode I vs Mode II

Mode I: (Toughening)

$$G_c^I = \begin{cases} a_1 \exp(a_2 C) + a_3 \exp(a_4 C) & C < 2.09\% \\ 0.62 & C \geq 2.09\% \end{cases}$$

$$a_1 = 0.70, \quad a_2 = -3.71, \quad a_3 = -0.49, \quad a_4 = -395.2$$

Mode II: (Embrittlement)

$$G_c^{II} = \begin{cases} b_1 C^2 + b_2 C + b_3 & C < 6.08\% \\ 0.096 & C \geq 6.08\% \end{cases}$$

$$b_1 = 31.58, \quad b_2 = -3.85, \quad b_3 = 0.21$$

[1] Sugiman, S., Putra, I.K.P. and Setyawan, P.D., *Polymer Degradation and Stability*, 134, pp.311-321 (2016).

[2] Johar, M., Chong, W.W.F., Kang, H.S. and Wong, K.J., 2019. *Polymer degradation and stability*, 165, pp.117-125.

Case study 1: Moisture content on the fracture toughness (mode I)

- The actual microstructure of the composite is simulated by an **embedded cell** in the fracture process zone, while the remaining area is homogenised to be an elastic anisotropic solid.

Microscopic crack growth and fracture toughness (Validation)

100 μm

[Canal et al. 2012]

$\Delta = 53 \mu m$

Cohesive zone (I) + PFM (M)

Constituents	E (GPa)	G_c (kJ/m ²)
Glass fibre	74	0.135
Epoxy matrix	3.5	0.010
Interface	5.0	0.005

G_c^{22} : Transverse fracture toughness

Now consider the moisture effect:

Diffused interface

Graded material properties

Moisture diffusion

The effect of moisture on crack trajectories

Experiment-Dry

Phase field damage

Cohesive zone-Dry

Diffuse interface-Dry

Diffuse interface-Wet

The effect of moisture on crack trajectories

- Diffuse interface model shows a diffused crack propagation.
- The moisture content impedes the crack propagation under mode I loading.

The effect of moisture on fracture toughness

- The fracture resistance increases with the increasing moisture contents.

Case study 2: A single notched sample under shear loading (mode II)

End-notch shear:

Material properties

Constituents	E (GPa)	G_c (kJ/m ²)	D (mm ² /s)	α
Flax fibre	10.2	2.1	1.19×10^{-6}	1.06
Polymer	3.5	1.2	1.45×10^{-6}	0.6
Interface	4.0	0.213	0.8×10^{-6}	0.1

Boundary condition

- The moisture concentration 7.45% is applied at the left edge and notch area.
- The end-notch shear load is applied.
- **Moisture and mechanical** loading are applied concurrently.

Comparison of Composite Failure Under Moisture Absorption

No Moisture

Moisture Absorption

□ The moisture degrades material toughness.

Case study 3: Representative volume element under shear loading (mode II)

Simple shear:

$$C = 7.45\%$$

P, δ

Material properties

Constituents	E (GPa)	G_c (kJ/m ²)	D (mm ² /s)	α
Flax fibre	10.2	2.1	1.19×10^{-6}	1.06
Polymer	3.5	1.2	1.45×10^{-6}	0.6
Interface	4.0	0.213	0.8×10^{-6}	0.1

Periodic boundary condition

- The opposite faces should deform identically:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} u_R - u_L = u_x \\ u_T - u_B = u_y \\ u_F - u_B = u_z \end{array} \right.$$

Comparison of Composite Failure Under Moisture Absorption

No Moisture

SDV_PHI
(Avg: 75%)

Moisture Absorption

SDV_CL
(Avg: 75%)

SDV_D
(Avg: 75%)

□ The moisture degrades material toughness.

Summary

- We have presented a new **phase field-based multi-physics framework** to model **moisture-induced degradation** in composite materials.
- A novel **diffuse interface approach** is presented to interpolate relevant properties along the fibre-matrix interface.
- The moisture contents promote the **mode I** fracture resistance and degrades the **mode II** fracture resistance.

Future work

- Conduct experiments under **environmental conditions** to further validate our model.
- Enhance the efficiency of the calculations by incorporating **adaptive** mesh refinement.

Thank you for your attention!

□ Open-source research codes:

- www.imperial.ac.uk/mechanics-materials/codes
- wtanlab.com/codes/

Research sponsors:

Industrial partners:

